

WRENCH

Whispers of Time

Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change

D3.1 | Climate models

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A Belmont Forum Project

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Introduction

In the WRENCH Project, a method is designed to investigate the impacts of climate change on cultural heritage sites. Cultural heritage is used as a narrative tool to make the complex risks of climate change visible and to raise public and political awareness. The technical foundation for achieving the aim of this project relies on methodology centered on climate models and the analysis of climate projection datasets over cultural heritage sites. The analysis focuses on a diverse set of globally significant cultural heritage sites, providing a broad assessment of climate vulnerability across various environmental and structural contexts. The sites examined in this study include (See Figure 1):

- Naples, Former Military Hospital (Italy)
- Montes de Galicia (Spain)
- Casertavecchia, Bell Tower (Italy)
- Ragusa, Duomo di San Giorgio (Italy)
- Durham Castle (UK)
- Matanza-Riachuelo River (Argentina)

Fig. 1 - WRENCH Pilot sites

The initial phases of the WRENCH Project, encompassing the development of climate models, the preparation of the necessary scenario data, and the production of model outputs, have been successfully completed and concluded on time in line with the defined work package objectives. This involved extensive data preparation through data acquisition and preliminary processing. Copernicus ERA5-Land reanalysis data was acquired for historical reference on hourly and daily time intervals. In addition, approximately 30 different General Circulation Model (GCM)-Regional Circulation Model (RCM) combinations of Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) model data (Gutowski et al. 2016) were downloaded from the ESGF Germany server, covering the historical, Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP)4.5 and RCP8.5 future scenarios. The GCM-RCM models used for specific climate variables (air temperature, humidity, wind, and precipitation) in historical, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 future scenarios are shown for EURO-11 datasets in Table 1 and SAM-44 in Table 2. SAM-44 refers to the South Asia Minor domain, typically used in the CORDEX framework, with a spatial resolution of approximately 44 km. EURO-11 refers to the European CORDEX domain, specifically at an approximately 12.5 km. GCM-RCM Combinations are pairings of a GCM that provides large-scale boundary conditions, and a RCM that downscales the data to a finer regional resolution.

These vast datasets underwent necessary preliminary preparations to commence the crucial bias correction procedures using the Quantile Delta Mapping (QDM) method, ensuring the reliability of the climate projections used for impact assessment on the heritage sites.

Parameter	Abbreviation	Reanalysis Dataset	GCM-RCM Combinations (Projections)
2m Air Temperature	T2	ERA5 Land	CNRM-CERFACS_CNRM-ALARO, CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53, CNRM-CM5?CNRM-ALADIN63, IPSL-IPSL_CM5A-WRF381P, NCC-NorESM1-M_DMI-HIRHAM5
Relative Humidity	RH	ERA5 Land	IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1_IPSL-WRF381P, NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1_DMI-HIRHAM5
Precipitation	PR	ERA5 Land	CNRM-CERFACS_CNRM-ALARO, CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN53, CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN63, IPSL-IPSL_CM5A-WRF381P
Wind Speed	WIND	ERA5 Land	CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1_CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17, MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1_CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17, NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1_DMI-HIRHAM5

Table 1: EURO-11 Domain Datasets

Parameter	Abbreviation	Reanalysis Dataset	GCM-RCM Combinations (Projections)
2m Air Temperature	T2	ERA5 Land	CCCma-CanESM2_UCAN-WRF341I, MPI-ESM-LR_MPI-CSC-REMO2009, NCC-NorESM1-M_SMHI-RCA4, GFDL-ESM2M_SMHI-RCA4, CSIRO-Mk3-6-0_SMHI-RCA4
Relative Humidity	RH	ERA5 Land	ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1_SMHI-RCA4, IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR_r1i1p1_SMHI-RCA4, MIROC-MIROC5_r1i1p1_SMHI-RCA4, NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1_SMHI-RCA4, NOAA-GFDL-GFDL-
Precipitation	PR	ERA5 Land	MPI-ESM-LR_REMO2009, CSIRO-QCCCE_SHMI-RCA4, CNRM-CM5_SMHI-RCA4, CCCma_CanESM2_UCAN-WRF341I
Wind Speed	WIND	ERA5 Land	CSIRO-QCCCE-CSIRO-Mk3-6-0_r1i1p1_SMHI-RCA4, MIROC-MIROC5_r1i1p1_SMHI-RCA4, MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_r1i1p1_SMHI-RCA4, NCC-NorESM1-M_r1i1p1_SMHI-RCA4

Table 2: SAM-44 Domain Datasets

Acquisition of GCM-RCM Data

Daily data for the necessary meteorological variables including 2-meter air temperature (T2), total precipitation (PR), relative humidity (RH), and the zonal (uas) and meridional (vas) components of the 10-meter wind (WIND) were obtained for the regions specified in the work plan. Approximately 30 GCM-RCM combinations of CORDEX models providing regional climate simulations for historical , RCP4.5, and RCP8.5 scenarios were downloaded for the EURO-11 and SAM-44 regions, with the specific model pairs for each variable (see Tables 1 and 2). As shown in these Tables, the specific GCM-RCM model combinations used for the analyses differ across each climate variable and are also dependent on the simulation type either historical, RCP4.5, or RCP8.5. Given that the analyses utilize ensemble estimates across all individual models, it is important to note the inherent uncertainty introduced by the specific, varied GCM-RCM combinations assigned to each climate variable and simulation type. Downloaded datasets for each variable at each heritage site are available in csv format at daily time interval for their historical and future scenario periods.

Acquisition of ERA5-Land Data

Copernicus ERA5-Land reanalysis data (a high-resolution reanalysis dataset of land surface variables from 1950 to the present, Hersbach et al., 2020; Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021) was obtained for the same domains and variables. The high-resolution ERA5-Land data (9 km) serves as a reference dataset to evaluate the performance of the GCM-RCM models and subsequently execute bias correction across both the historical as reference period (1970-2005) and future scenario period (2006-2100). The data from GCM-RCM models were corrected using the QDM bias correction method (Gumus et al., 2023, Guo et al., 2019, Tong et al. 2021) at daily time interval, completing the data pre-processing step. All data sets in NetCDF format were converted to RData format to enable fast and consistent analysis in the R environment, preserving their spatial (lat-lon) and temporal (daily/monthly) structures as multi-dimensional data arrays. Downloaded datasets for each variable at each heritage site are also available in csv format at hourly time interval for the historical period.

Spatial Distribution Analyses

Using the bias-corrected data, map-based spatial distribution analyses were performed across the entire EURO-11 domain. Figures 2-5 show the annual total precipitation, relative humidity, temperature, and wind speed values based on ERA5-Land reanalysis observations, the bias-corrected historical period model averages, and the anomaly (difference) values between far future (2065-2100) and historical (1970-2005) periods produced for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The results show a high compatibility between the model outputs (spatial variations within the domain) obtained after bias correction for each variable (precipitation, humidity, temperature, and wind) and the ERA5-Land observation data. Specifically, under the pessimistic scenario (RCP8.5), the increase in annual total precipitation over central and northern Europe is projected to be approximately 100-200 mm/year higher compared to the optimistic scenario (RCP4.5) results (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Displays the Mean Annual Precipitation based on ERA5-Land (top-left), the bias-corrected GCM-RCM ensemble mean for the historical reference period (top-right), and the respective far-future changes from the reference period projected by the RCP4.5 (bottom-left) and RCP8.5 (bottom-right) scenarios. Four selected Heritage Sites with purple color are also shown. HIST means historical.

In the Mediterranean climate region, where countries like Italy and France are located (Heritage sites 3,4,5,6), the projected decrease in annual precipitation under the RCP8.5 scenario is approximately 100 mm/year greater than under the RCP4.5 scenario. Due to the greater increase in annual precipitation anomalies over Northern Europe under the RCP8.5 scenario, the overall mean anomaly is higher (89.38 mm) compared to the RCP4.5 scenario (55.85 mm). In parallel with temperature increases, Western Europe (such as the UK, Portugal, Spain, and France) shows a 2-4% greater decrease in relative humidity under the pessimistic scenario compared to the optimistic scenario (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Displays the Mean Relative Humidity based on ERA5-Land (top-left), the bias-corrected GCM-RCM ensemble mean for the historical reference period (top-right), and the respective far-future changes from the reference period projected by the RCP4.5 (bottom-left) and RCP8.5 (bottom-right) scenarios. Four selected Heritage Sites with purple color are also shown. HIST means historical.

In these regions, while the air's moisture holding capacity increases with rising temperatures (Figure 4), the actual moisture content decreases. This leads to an increase in water vapor stress in the air over these regions. Temperature increases are much more pronounced in the pessimistic scenario, exceeding 6oC over eastern and especially northern Europe (Figure 4). Domain averaged temperature anomaly increases for RCP8.5 and RCP4.5 are 4.26oC and 3.64oC, respectively.

Figure 4: Displays the Mean Air Temperature based on ERA5-Land (top-left), the bias-corrected GCM-RCM ensemble mean for the historical reference period (top-right), and the respective far-future changes from the reference period projected by the RCP4.5 (bottom-left) and RCP8.5 (bottom-right) scenarios. Four selected Heritage Sites with purple color are also shown. HIST means historical.

According to the results of both scenarios, wind values are projected to increase across the entire EURO-11 domain in the future, with this increase being approximately 0.1-0.2 m/s greater in the pessimistic scenario (parallel to greater temperature increases) (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Displays the Mean Wind based on ERA5-Land (top-left), the bias-corrected GCM-RCM ensemble mean for the historical reference period (top-right), and the respective far-future changes from the reference period projected by the RCP4.5 (bottom-left) and RCP8.5 (bottom-right) scenarios. Four selected Heritage Sites with purple color are also shown. HIST means historical.

Using the bias-corrected data, map-based spatial distribution analyses were performed across the entire SAM-44 domain. Figures 6-9 present the annual total precipitation, relative humidity, temperature, and wind speed values based on ERA5-Land reanalysis observations, the bias-corrected historical period ensemble model averages, and the anomaly (difference) values between 1965-2100 and historical period produced for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. As a result of bias correction, the model outputs for all variables (precipitation, humidity, temperature, and wind) show high compatibility with the ERA5-Land observations in terms of spatial distribution within the domain.

Figure 6: Displays the Mean Annual Precipitation based on ERA5-Land (top-left), the bias-corrected GCM-RCM ensemble mean for the historical reference period (top-right), and the respective far-future changes from the reference period projected by the RCP4.5 (bottom-left) and RCP8.5 (bottom-right) scenarios. The selected Heritage Site with purple color is also shown. HIST means historical

The mean annual precipitation across the entire continent is 1604 mm based on ERA5-Land data, which increases to approximately 1681 mm according to the bias-corrected ensemble mean of the GCMs (Figure 6). The pattern of precipitation anomaly changes is similar for both scenarios; however, the magnitude of decrease is greater under RCP8.5 (-79.16 mm) compared to RCP4.5 (-65.89 mm) (Figure 6).

Figure 7: Displays the Mean Relative Humidity based on ERA5-Land (top-left), the bias-corrected GCM-RCM ensemble mean for the historical reference period (top-right), and the respective far-future changes from the reference period projected by the RCP4.5 (bottom-left) and RCP8.5 (bottom-right) scenarios. The selected Heritage Site with red color is also shown. HIST means historical.

Parallel to the temperature increase, the pessimistic scenario (RCP8.5) results in South America are projected to cause a 4-6% increase in relative humidity, while the optimistic scenario (RCP4.5) results in a 3-4% increase (Figure 7). In these regions, the air's moisture holding capacity increases with rising temperatures, and there is also an increase in absolute humidity.

Figure 8: Displays the Mean Air Temperature based on ERA5-Land (top-left), the bias-corrected GCM-RCM ensemble mean for the historical reference period (top-right), and the respective far-future changes from the reference period projected by the RCP4.5 (bottom-left) and RCP8.5 (bottom-right) scenarios. The selected Heritage Site with blue color is also shown. HIST means historical.

Consequently, the air's water vapor stress increases. Both the ERA5-Land data and the bias-corrected ensemble mean yielded similar mean continental temperatures of 20.84°C and 20.66°C, respectively (Figure 8). Temperature increases are much more pronounced in the pessimistic scenario, with increases exceeding 4°C to 5°C particularly in the northern and eastern parts of South America (Figure 8).

Figure 9: Displays the Mean Wind Speed based on ERA5-Land (top-left), the bias-corrected GCM-RCM ensemble mean for the historical reference period (top-right), and the respective far-future changes from the reference period projected by the RCP4.5 (bottom-left) and RCP8.5 (bottom-right) scenarios. The selected Heritage Site with red color is also shown. HIST means historical.

The spatial distribution of wind speed anomaly changes is also very similar between the two scenarios (Figure 9). A slight increase of about 0.1 m/s in wind speed is projected around the heritage site under the RCP8.5 scenario (Figure 9).

Time Series

Analyses

In addition to analyses showing spatial changes, annual time series covering the historical (1970–2005), RCP4.5, and RCP8.5 (2006–2100) scenarios for each climate variable were generated for the six pilot regions specified in the work plan, using only the grid points matching the coordinates of these regions (Figures 10–13). In these analyses, the annual time series are shown with uncertainty ranges corresponding to the number of GCM-RCM models used together with the ensemble mean values along with projection and historical periods. Thus, the ranges of model-induced uncertainties in the projections of the variables are also provided. During the historical period, ERA5-Land data are also presented for comparison. The GCM-related time series are shown using their bias-corrected datasets. For all climate variables (annual precipitation, relative humidity, air temperature, and wind speed) across all heritage sites (Figures 10–13), the ERA5-Land data remain within the model uncertainty range throughout the historical period, exhibiting realistic fluctuations. This indicates that the GCM-RCM ensembles adequately capture the temporal variability of the observed climate. Within the scope of these analyses, the time-dependent trends of regional climate changes in the study areas were analyzed in detail.

According to Figure 10, the annual mean precipitation is projected to remain largely consistent with historical averages. However, by the end of the 21st century, annual precipitation is projected to increase by up to 40–80 mm in the Durham region and decrease by up to 35 mm in the Duomo di San Giorgio region, particularly under the RCP8.5 scenario (Figure 10). At Duomo di San Giorgio, the mean annual precipitation decreases from 491 mm in the historical period to 481 mm under RCP4.5, and further to 457 mm under RCP8.5. At Durham, the mean annual precipitation increases from 756 mm in the historical period to 796 mm under RCP4.5, and further to 831 mm under RCP8.5. The absence of a distinct trend across all pilot regions, except for Durham and Duomo di San Giorgio, suggests that total annual precipitation under both emission scenarios will exhibit limited temporal variation in the future. However, year-to-year and periodic variability are evident at all sites, while the results from both scenarios closely follow each other and show minimal discrepancies (Figure 10).

In the Matanza–Riachuelo and Durham regions, the temperature increase becomes much more pronounced after the 2050s and 2080s, respectively, under the RCP8.5 scenario compared to RCP4.5, as the two scenarios begin to diverge after these periods (Figure 11). In contrast, for the other four study regions, this divergence—marked by a noticeable temperature rise under RCP8.5—occurs between 2060 and 2070 (Figure 11). Generally, while the trend in temperature increases is similar for both scenarios in all study regions until these years, the trend slope for the pessimistic scenario becomes much steeper afterward. Mean temperature increases from historical to future period are given for all six sites under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios in Table 3. The highest temperature increases—2.28°C and 2.22°C—were observed at Duomo di San Giorgio, Naples, and Casertavecchia under the RCP8.5 scenario, while

Heritage Sites	RCP4.5 (°C)	RCP8.5 (°C)
Matanza-Riachuelo River (Argentina)	0.78	1.64
Montes de Galicia (Spain)	1.59	1.88
Naples, Former Military Hospital (Italy)	1.93	2.22
Durham Castle (UK)	1.54	1.78
Ragusa, Duomo di San Giorgio, (Italy)	1.95	2.28
Casertavecchia, Bell Tower (Italy)	1.93	2.22

Table 3: Mean changes from the historical period (1970-2005) to the future period (2006-2100) under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 for all six heritage sites.

The Durham and Montes de Galicia sites show no significant trend or a slight decrease in relative humidity from the historical to future periods under both emission scenarios (Figure 12). In contrast, the other four sites exhibit an increase in relative humidity—up to 1.18% under RCP8.5 (Naples/Casertavecchia sites, Figure 12) and up to 0.7% under RCP4.5 (Montaza site, Figure 12). An increase in relative humidity, alongside rising air temperatures, indicates a trend toward a wetter climate. Conversely, a decrease in relative humidity under the same warming trend suggests a shift toward a drier climate, with an associated increase in temperature depression.

Casertavecchia, Naples, Matanza–Riachuelo, and Duomo di San Giorgio sites exhibit an increasing trend in wind speed from the historical to future periods, ranging from 0.03 to 0.05 m/s under RCP 4.5 and from 0.05 to 0.07 m/s under RCP8.5 (Figure 13). In contrast, the Durham site shows a decreasing trend of approximately 0.06 m/s under RCP4.5 and 0.08 m/s under RCP 8.5. Montes de Galicia site shows no significant trend in wind speed under either scenario. Significant interannual variability in wind speed is also evident under these trend conditions (Figure 13).

Heritage Sites	Periods	Temperature (°C)	Precipitation (mm/year)	Wind (m/s)	Relative Humidity (%)
Matanza-Riachuelo River (Argentina)	RCP4.5 (2006-2040)	-0.14	-17.40	-0.08	-0.97
	RCP4.5 (2051-2070)	0.56	0.98	-0.05	-0.60
	RCP4.5 (2071-2100)	-1.21	-8.26	0.01	-0.42
	RCP8.5 (2006-2040)	-0.01	19.07	0.02	-0.68
	RCP8.5 (2051-2070)	0.64	-1.82	0.07	0.00
	RCP8.5 (2071-2100)	-1.02	-17.78	-0.04	-0.89
Montes de Galicia (Spain)	RCP4.5 (2006-2040)	0.12	-5.05	-0.06	-0.47
	RCP4.5 (2051-2070)	-0.45	-1.16	0.02	-2.03
	RCP4.5 (2071-2100)	1.11	2.76	0.04	0.55
	RCP8.5 (2006-2040)	0.27	-0.77	0.08	-0.45
	RCP8.5 (2051-2070)	-0.26	4.78	0.02	-0.94
	RCP8.5 (2071-2100)	1.27	-2.27	0.01	-0.77
Naples, Former Military Hospital (Italy)	RCP4.5 (2006-2040)	0.76	5.12	0.01	1.87
	RCP4.5 (2051-2070)	-0.27	2.57	0.02	1.20
	RCP4.5 (2071-2100)	1.71	14.23	0.05	0.99
	RCP8.5 (2006-2040)	0.70	23.58	-0.05	-0.39
	RCP8.5 (2051-2070)	-0.33	10.17	0.00	-0.96
	RCP8.5 (2071-2100)	1.50	14.48	-0.02	0.85
Durham Castle (UK)	RCP4.5 (2006-2040)	0.54	-0.21	0.14	-0.22
	RCP4.5 (2051-2070)	0.06	-1.14	-0.07	-1.29
	RCP4.5 (2071-2100)	1.28	2.95	-0.04	0.31
	RCP8.5 (2006-2040)	0.61	0.17	0.04	0.12
	RCP8.5 (2051-2070)	-0.13	2.28	-0.13	-0.59
	RCP8.5 (2071-2100)	1.47	4.26	0.06	0.53
Ragusa, Duomo di San Giorgio, (Italy)	RCP4.5 (2006-2040)	0.71	5.31	0.01	0.86
	RCP4.5 (2051-2070)	-0.23	4.99	0.02	1.18
	RCP4.5 (2071-2100)	1.64	1.57	0.07	0.52
	RCP8.5 (2006-2040)	0.83	9.37	-0.08	-0.21
	RCP8.5 (2051-2070)	-0.18	7.48	-0.02	-0.33
	RCP8.5 (2071-2100)	1.56	2.62	-0.01	0.75
Casertavecchia, Bell Tower (Italy)	RCP4.5 (2006-2040)	0.73	5.06	0.02	1.84
	RCP4.5 (2051-2070)	0.50	3.01	0.03	0.44
	RCP4.5 (2071-2100)	2.39	14.27	0.05	0.34
	RCP8.5 (2006-2040)	1.12	23.49	-0.04	-0.36
	RCP8.5 (2051-2070)	-0.36	10.57	0.01	-1.67
	RCP8.5 (2071-2100)	1.47	14.57	-0.02	0.49

Table 4: Mean values from the historical period to different future periods under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 for all six heritage sites.

Figure 10. Annual average time series of precipitation, relative humidity, air temperature, and wind speed for the Bell Tower Casertavecchia site are presented for the period 1970–2100. The results include bias-corrected outputs from individual model pairs, the ensemble mean, ERA5–Land data, and projections under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emission scenarios. The model uncertainty range is also shown. In addition, the mean and standard deviation for the historical, reference (ERA5–Land), and future scenario periods are provided.

Figure 11. Annual average time series of precipitation, relative humidity, air temperature, and wind speed for the Duomo di San Giorgio site are presented for the period 1970–2100. The results include bias-corrected outputs from individual model pairs, the ensemble mean, ERA5–Land data, and projections under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emission scenarios. The model uncertainty range is also shown. In addition, the mean and standard deviation for the historical, reference (ERA5–Land), and future scenario periods are provided.

Figure 12. Annual average time series of precipitation, relative humidity, air temperature, and wind speed for the Durham Castle site are presented for the period 1970–2100. The results include bias-corrected outputs from individual model pairs, the ensemble mean, ERA5-Land data, and projections under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emission scenarios. The model uncertainty range is also shown. In addition, the mean and standard deviation for the historical, reference (ERA5-Land), and future scenario periods are provided.

Annual Ensemble Mean Precipitation: Former Military Hospital Naples

Annual Ensemble Mean Relative Humidity: Former Military Hospital Naples

Annual Ensemble Mean Temperature: Former Military Hospital Naples

Annual Ensemble Mean Wind Speed: Former Military Hospital Naples

Figure 13. Annual average time series of precipitation, relative humidity, air temperature, and wind speed for the Former Military Hospital Naples site are presented for the period 1970–2100. The results include bias-corrected outputs from individual model pairs, the ensemble mean, ERA5-Land data, and projections under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emission scenarios. The model uncertainty range is also shown. In addition, the mean and standard deviation for the historical, reference (ERA5-Land), and future scenario periods are provided.

Figure 14. Annual average time series of precipitation, relative humidity, air temperature, and wind speed for the Montes de Galicia site are presented for the period 1970–2100. The results include bias-corrected outputs from individual model pairs, the ensemble mean, ERA5-Land data, and projections under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emission scenarios. The model uncertainty range is also shown. In addition, the mean and standard deviation for the historical, reference (ERA5-Land), and future scenario periods are provided.

Annual Ensemble Mean Precipitation: Matanza-Riachuelo

Annual Ensemble Mean Relative Humidity: Matanza-Riachuelo

Annual Ensemble Mean Temperature: Matanza-Riachuelo

Annual Ensemble Mean Wind Speed: Matanza-Riachuelo

Figure 15. Annual average time series of precipitation, relative humidity, air temperature, and wind speed for the Matanza-Riachuelo site are presented for the period 1970–2100. The results include bias-corrected outputs from individual model pairs, the ensemble mean, ERA5-Land data, and projections under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emission scenarios. The model uncertainty range is also shown. In addition, the mean and standard deviation for the historical, reference (ERA5-Land), and future scenario periods are provided.

References

- Gumus B, Oruc S, Yucel I, Yilmaz MT. Impacts of Climate Change on Extreme Climate Indices in Türkiye Driven by High-Resolution Downscaled CMIP6 Climate Models. *Sustainability*. **2023**, 15(9):7202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097202>.
- Guo Q, Chen J, Zhang X, Shen M, Chen H, Guo S. A new two-stage multivariate quantile mapping method for bias correcting climate model outputs. *Clim. Dyn.* **2019**, 53, 3603–3623.
- Gutowski Jr, W J, Giorgi F, Timbal B, Frigon A, Jacob D, Kang H.-S, Raghavan K, Lee B, Lennard C, Nikulin G, O'Rourke E, Rixen M, Solman S, Stephenson T, and Tangang F. WCRP COordinated Regional Downscaling EXperiment (CORDEX): a diagnostic MIP for CMIP6, *Geosci. Model Dev.* **2016**, 9, 4087–4095, doi:10.5194/gmd-9-4087-2016.
- Tong Y, Gao X, Han Z, Xu Y, Xu Y, Giorgi F. Bias correction of temperature and precipitation over China for RCM simulations using the QM and QDM methods. *Clim. Dyn.* **2021**, 57, 1425–1443.
- Hersbach H, Bell B, Berrisford P, Hirahara S, Horanyi A, Muñoz-Sabater J, Nicolas J, Peubey C, Radu R, Schepers D, et al. The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* **2020**, 146, 1999–2049.
- Muñoz-Sabater J, Dutra E, Agustí-Panareda A, Albergel C, Arduini G, Balsamo G, Boussetta S, Choulga M, Harrigan S, Hersbach H, et al. ERA5-Land: A state-of-the-art global reanalysis dataset for land applications. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data.* **2021**, 13, 4349–4383.

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A Belmont Forum Project
2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18800320>

PCI2024-153536

